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SYNTACTIC LINKS CREATED BY PROFESSOR A.M. MUKHIN

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on syntactic relations and their features in language. Research methodology problems are not often addressed in linguistics. Logically, consciously choosing a method within the requirements of this science helps to find a solution to the research faster. The first of the methods is based on theory, the second is based on practice, and it is not a symbol of any theory, but a product of the reality of life and the universal laws of intellectual and psychological development of a scientist.

Key words: methodology, linguistics, paradigm, types of syntactic binding, syntactic relations, syntactic conjunction, complex object, unites a higher element, unites a lower element, methods, syntactic links.

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PROFESSOR A.M.MUXIN TOMONIDAN YARATILGAN SINTAKTIK ALOQALAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada sintaktik munosabatlar va ularning tildagi xususiyatlariga e'tibor qaratilgan. Tilshunoslikda tadqiqot metodologiyasi muammolariga ko'pincha hal etilmaydi. Mantiqan bu fan talablari doirasida metodlarni ongli ravishda tanlash tadqiqotga tezroq yechim topishga yordam beradi. Usullarning birinchisi nazariya, ikkinchisi amaliyotga asoslangan bo'lib, u hech qanday nazariyaning ramzi emas, balki hayot haqiqati va olimning aqliy-psixologik rivojlanishining umuminsoniy qonuniyatlari mahsulidir.

Kalit so'zlar: metodologiya, lingvistika, paradigma, sintaktik bog'lanish turlari, sintaktik munosabatlar, sintaktik bo'lanish, murakkab bog'lanish, yuqori elementni birlashishi, quyi elementni birlashishi, metodlar, sintaktik bog'lanmalar.

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СИНТАКТИЧЕСКИЕ СВЯЗИ, СОЗДАННЫЕ ПРОФЕССОРОМ А.М.МУХИНЫМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена синтаксическим отношениям и их особенностям в языке. Проблемы методологии исследования в языкознании часто не решаются. Логично, что сознательный выбор методов в рамках требований этой науки поможет быстрее найти решение исследования. Первый из методов основан на теории, а второй - на практике и является не символом какой-либо теории, а продуктом реальности жизни и универсальных законов умственно-психологического развития ученого.

Ключивые слова: методология, языкознание, парадигма, виды синтаксической связи, синтаксические отношения, синтаксическая связь, сложный объект, объединяет вышестоящий элемент, объединяет низший элемент, методы, синтаксические связи.

Introduction. If the work is done according to a certain paradigm, according to existing patterns, reflection is often considered superfluous, and within a certain tradition within this paradigm. As the researcher consciously strives for initial methodological precision, the problem of method inevitably comes to the fore because it is intrinsically linked. The most basic questions of linguistics: in the end, the method of selection (or formation) is mainly determined by how the scientist sees the object, representing its nature, etc. As one of the recent examples, I refer to the series of monographs by O.V. Leshchak [Leshchak 2008; 2009; 2010]; it is significant that the first volume of this cycle is entirely devoted to the development of research methodology.

The question of method does not arise in studies that consider the types of syntactic binding; this applies in any case to most of the concepts discussed below. At the same time, there are works of a slightly different type, defined at least by their stylistic articulation. Apparently, such a difference allows us to guess that the results in the second type of document should be more reliable. Analysis shows that such a prediction would be hasty. Consider several concepts that represent the system in one way or another through syntactic relations. An important caveat: we proceed from the idea that the concepts of syntactic relation and syntactic relation are not unique. This is not a reason to accept the premise. As with what my point of view is, beyond this point, there is a whole tradition which it would be wrong to ignore when talking about the problem at hand.

1. At the heart of O. Jespersen's syntactic system are two categories: association and connection. The first usually corresponds to the concept of subordination phrases; secondly, O. Jespersen clearly means structures, or in a hidden (folding) way that reflects the action of predication; among them are included not only propositions, but also so-called constructions. "Complex object" (complex object, cf. His example: I heard him sing), secondary predication (he didn't paint the door red), and various infinitive constructions. The terms "junction" and "nexus" are so universally used by O. Jespersen that it can be argued that they also denote two broad types of syntactic units, two types of syntactic relations, and two types of connections. The interpretation of the nexus, in particular, as a type of syntactic connection, is clear, for example, in the following statement of the author: "'New" is not always located in the predicate; but it always lies in the connection of the subject and the predicate, i.e., in the fact of combining two components, or, in other words, in the "joint" [Jespersen 2006: 164; author failure].

2. The first part of his extensive work, "Syntactic Conjunction," is very concise in its definition of connection: In fact, what we call conjunction refers to the word "syntax" itself, from the Greek "arrangement", which means "to put in order." In addition, the concept that reflects the inner essence of this sentence corresponds to the inner "inner form of language" sprachformi by V. Humboldt [Tenière 1988: 23]. In other words, L. Tenier refuses to attempt to define an ontologically syntactic conjunction. Moreover, he is more precise: "Syntactic conjunctions establish relations of dependence between words." Each conjunction unites a higher element with a lower element "[Tenière 1988: 24].

Thus, if we consider L. Tenier's system from the point of view of the traditional classification of connections, there will always be a syntactic connection for it. All the connections are subordinate, including the connection between the subject and the predicate, because it recognizes the verbal

concept of the sentence. 1. What about composition? L. Tenier does not use such a concept (and therefore, the opposite of composition-subordination is not in the foundations of his system). However, he introduces the concept of a compound of a fundamentally different nature, not a syntactic connection (in his interpretation). 2. This result is a "bifurcation" or more broadly, a "multiplication" one of the "nodes" of syntactic structure, a multiplication that does not affect the "structural order" and therefore the semantic structure of the sentence [Tenière 1988: 30; 337]. In other words, Tenier's union is what is often called a composition connection. If requested, it can be seen in the following formula by L. Tenier that contradicts the original rules: "When two terms are doubled, performing the same structural task is similar to each other, and the identity functions lead to a connection between them." This connection creates the essence of connection [Tenière 1988: 337; my cursive.-M.D.].

Indeed, or here we are not talking about syntactic communication (but then the question arises: about which if we are talking about syntax?); or-if you mean connection, which corresponds to the original definition-establishes subordination between two "nodes" (but this contradicts the thesis of their equal functionality and implies the introduction of the concept of union makes it useless); or syntactic connections still do not always "establish relations between words connections", and the original definition does not cover all syntactic connections, but only a part of them. However, it does not matter to us; what is important is that it is ultimately a calculation. In the system of L. Tenier, there are two types of syntactic connection (correlative with the concepts of content and subordination) and subordinate connection. The conjunction also covers what is called a predicative conjunction in other systems.

But it should be noted that L. Tenier (correctly) uses the contrast of parataxis and hypotaxis along with the concepts of syntactic connection and connection, although the place of this contrast in his system is not defined. In one case, he establishes the identity between the pairs "parataxis-hypotaxis" and "constituent structure-subordinate structure" concepts, and here he uses the term "constitutive." relationship" and "subordinate relationship":

1. The last type of metataxis to be considered here is when a coordinating structure in one language corresponds to a subordinate structure in another language. 2. At the same structural level, consisting of two symbols located above the coordinate structure. This arrangement of signs is called parataxis; Greek para here means that two nodes are located next to each other. The Greek term "parataxis" is of French origin and is equivalent to the Latin term. "content" of coordination. The stem is represented by a single horizontal line with a coordinating connection. 3. Conversely, a subordinate structure is the location of one expressed below another. Such an arrangement of signifieds is called hypotaxis; the Greek nypo means here that one knot is below another. The Greek term Hypotaxis is equivalent to the Latin term in French. obey "obey". In the stem, the subordinate relation is described using one vertical line [Tenière 1988: 328; author's w / w font, my italics]. -M.D.].

2. In another case, L. Tenière defines parataxis as "a simple way of connecting the syntactic connection of one verb node with another" as "a real semantic connection without a marker." [Tenière 1988: 538]. This feature is correct. "Speech is given directly to connections in the design." It is clear that parataxis cannot be equated with composition here; furthermore, parataxis here consists only of the juxtaposition of components, the direct connection of the structure's components. It is not possible to determine (semantic or grammatical) equality with proper speech; it is not so accidental that the common interpretation of the relationship between these components is as an object, that is, as a type of subordinate relationship. Thus, the opposite of parataxis although there is hypotaxis in the work, L. Tenier uses it, its content and place in the syntactic system are not clearly defined by the author's thoughts.

3. L. Elmslev categorizes all syntactic connections into three types: interdependence ("interconnections in which one member presupposes the existence of another and vice versa"); determinations ("one-way" dependencies in which one term presupposes the existence of the other but not vice versa"); and constellations ("freer dependencies in which both members agree but neither presupposes the existence of the other"). Obviously, in this case, such types of relations are different

types of relations. Starting from dependence, there is nothing but relations; the subcategories of dependence do not give a typology of relations, but a typology of different types of the same relations. 4. A.I. Smirnitsky distinguishes the following 4 types of syntactic communication: a) predicative-connection between the main members of the sentence; b) attributive-the relationship between definition and defined; c) complement (or adverb)-"the most characteristic of the complement and the case <...> is its main and most characteristic, unlike the attributive connection, which always remains with words included in this connection." In addition to the proposition, it develops sentences not as specific members but as independent units of syntactic groups; d) copulative-a connection between members of the same gender [Smirnitsky 1957: 173–184].

A.I. Smirnitsky placed the sentence as a grammatical unit at the center of his syntactic system, as a central category. He considers sentences to be predicative. Therefore, as the basis for the classification of connections, he chooses the role that this or that connection plays in the constitution of the proposal. A hierarchy is being built: predicative relations (the most important) complete (second in importance, because it includes "words... as independent units") attributive copulative. A.I. Smirnitsky is the main character in the system. From our point of view, Smirnitsky has two rules: 1) not only distinguishing the predicative link as a special type but also recognizing its leading role in the organization of the proposition; and 2) distinguishing between attributive and complex relations. However, the second position seems weak.

They are never "given, ready-made," as the author writes. When we are talking about examples like a little boy is "a little boy", my brother is "my brother", his life is "his life" and so on. (examples of A.I. Smirnitsky), the author's thesis looks convincing. But the same connection occurs in similar combinations when the correlation of the definition with the defined is unexpected, in combinations that are in no way recognized as "pre-given, ready-made." At least the moon of envy, dear perfection, stone borders⁴ (W. Shakespeare, *Romeo and Juliet*, Act II, Scene II): without it, not only poetry, but also qualities of good speech in any image, mind, etc., are its varieties.

Likewise, A.I. Smirnitsky calls it complete but does not always include the words "as independent units" in the sentence: it is known that many verbs, and besides them, nouns, adjectives, and adverbs-do not understand the root. Its lexical meaning is an obligatory complement, but it remains a verbal distributive at the same time; that is, it is not formed. The performance ended earlier than usual. However, if we refuse to distinguish attributive and complex relations, then we must combine them and in this case, we encounter the traditional triad: predicative, subordinate (=attributive + complementary), and coordinative (=copulative) relations. However, it should be noted that A.I. Smirnitsky was one of the scientists who worked on this triad including the predicative link! and manifested itself in the local syntactic tradition.

5. A.M. Mukhin, studying the structure of a simple sentence (based on English), distinguishes between 1) core predicative connection; 2) predicative communication without core; 3) subordinate relationship; 4) positive connection; 5) coordinating communication; and 6) input communication [Mukhin 2004]. The first two types include what O. Jespersen covers with the concept Nexus (although they do not exhaust the content of this concept): (1) a two-way connection between the subject and the predicate; and (2) a two-way connection with the predicate, the connection between a component (for example, an object) and a secondary predicate to it (see the above examples of O. Jespersen and cited by A.M. Mukhin Examples from S. Maugham: I didn't think he could, but I found him talking to a worker. Subordinate A.M. Mukhin calls for subordination (according to the English tradition, subordination); however, in his interpretation, subordinate relations are not simply one-way (which would be obvious)-they are directed from subordinate component to subordinate: if in a given sentence some word is formed:

To be interpreted as components... relative to the predicate, [then] the latter... does not correspond to them. This means that the syntax is directed not from the predicate to the specified elements but vice versa. [Mukhin 2004: 33]. Coordinating connection (also known as composition in English): the same as composition. According to his A.M. Mukhin, the most important distinguishing feature, consists of non-directionality: unlike all other types of communication, "coordinating communication does not serve as a basis for opposing one of the connected components to another"

[Mukhin 2004: 92]. By introducing the concept of input communication, A.M. Mukhin brings his position closer to the point of view of syntacticians who tried to prove the introduction of the input component at the same time to the grammatical structure of the sentence. In the author's interpretation, this is a one-sided relationship, similar to the subordinate but different from it. orientation from the dependent component (in this case, input) not to one dominant word, but to the entire sentence.

Finally, an appositive conjunction is a conjunction between an adjunct and the noun being identified. Usually, in this case, either a type of subordinating relationship (incomplete agreement or nominative suffix) or a coordinating conjunction. Both solutions are vulnerable because 1) the vector of dependence in appositive compounds is difficult to determine, or usually undetectable, and the possibility of replacing the apposition and the antecedent is almost always present, invalidating the assumption of subordination; and 2) compositional relations can always be renewed by compositional connection, that is, the introduction of a coordinating union; operations such as positive combinations are not allowed. Therefore, A.M. Mukhin's position deserves support. In this case, it is important to show a special type of communication and emphasize its distinguishing feature: the application is not only connected with the previous sentence, but also indirectly, through it, it is connected with the connected component of the previous sentence, appearing in metathesis application and previous [Mukhin 2004: 78]. Another thing is that questions such as this name the conjunction and determine its place in the system of syntactic relations.

A.M. Mukhin's concept is, in a certain sense, against the above concepts of O. Jespersen, L. Elmslev, L. Tenier, and even A.I. Smirnitsky. If the second one can be called "minimalist," he tries to find the most basic things in the proposal, types of syntactic connections, abstracting from details, while the first one, on the contrary, tries to take everything into account. However, the system of syntactic relations built by A.M. Mukhin, in fact, repeats the structure of the sentence-of course, how the author sees it. The researcher does not consider it necessary to distinguish between the components that traditional grammar calls "secondary elements" of the proposition. All the elements, called definitions, adverbs, and cases, are essentially one and the same component of the proposition, that is, dependent. They can be represented by different parts of speech [Mukhin 2004: 4].

It was this decision that allowed the author to distinguish one type of connection subordinate; otherwise, the system would probably have 8 rather than 6 conjunction types, containing a determiner (or attributive), an adverb (or subject) instead of a subordinate clause, and subordinate clause⁷. It should also be noted that the basis for all of A.M. Mukhin's conclusions is served by experiences consisting of one or the omission of another component of the sentence. In the case of the replacement or replacement of components, the component is considered a synonym. The author does not take into account the official signs of postulated connections. At the same time, it is clear that the proposition is missing some component, and to make sure that the proposition without it is incomplete, incapable, etc., we get information about this component: it is required by the structure of the sentence, its constituent is introduced as a part, that is, we get information about the syntactic relationship in which this component is included: After all, the structure is a sum of components and the relationship between them.

But at the same time, we do not get any information about how this relationship is embodied in the verbal structure of the sentence. Mukhin's system of syntactic relations is actually a system of syntactic relations; precisely because of this, it actually repeats the structure of propositions in the author's understanding. The same goes for A.I. Smirnitsky also applies to the concept. 6. V.G. Gack in "Theoretical Grammar of the French Language" devotes a separate chapter to syntactic relations. First of all, it directly and indirectly gives a clear definition of syntactic connection: The main units of syntax are two or more components that have a certain structure, consisting of a phrase and a sentence (usually)-syntactic connection and semantic relations expressed through [Gak 2000: 501]. - It follows that syntactic connection is understood as a way or means of expression of structural-semantic relations between components of phrases or sentences. This concept is further deepened:

"Syntactic connection is a two-dimensional entity, characterized by a certain form and a certain generalized meaning," and the form of communication is the actual means of expression, and

the content is "relationships, things in the objective world that can be established between events" [Gak 2000: 502].

The three main semantic types of relations: equality, dependency, and indistinguishability correspond to three main types from the point of view of representation. composition, subordination, and approach (connection is not expressed by a special morphological or syntactic means, but only intonation) (Similarly there: w / w font is mine.-M.D.). The author combines composition and juxtaposition in the more general concept of parataxis since, in his opinion, these two types of communication constitute "relationships." "Syntactically equal elements" can be defined by the term hypotaxis, which represents dependence [Gak 2000: 503]. V.G. Gak "Means of syntactic expression are relations." These include agreement, management, lexical means (prepositions, conjunctions, articles), desemantized words, ordered words, intonation.

In the system of connections built by the author, there are places for mutual communication predicative V.G. Gak, making the appropriate reservation (referring to F. de Saussure, who indicated the interdependence that occurs in this case), chooses the decision to consider this dependence as an agreement "in the broadest sense" [Gak 2000: 510]. 7. As can be seen from the above comment, there is no unity in the theory of syntax about the nature of syntactic communication; there is no single approach to defining types of communication and their classification. The main thing that becomes clear is the syntactic connection and the actual correspondence of syntactic concepts. This coincidence allows us to judge the basic generality of the method that unites all these systems, although, when I say "basic generality," I mean only an incomplete identity of the method.

The concept of connection type may correspond to the concept of syntactic type units, but in this case, the unit is defined on the basis of the relationship between the components in it (association and connection by O. Jespersen). The classification of communication types can actually repeat the classification of sentence members (and even members): such typologies as those of A.I. Smirnitsky and A.M. Mukhin The members of the sentence, as you can see, differ according to established syntactic relations. L. Elmslev's typologies are also related to syntactic relations, L. Tenier and "traditional". Gaka combines the concepts of relations (content and transmission) and opens on the basis of conceptually determined, formal appearance (renewal), but the latter eventually enters parataxis, as a result of which the final relations are again dominated by typologies.

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